

Technical report: Literature review of valuation studies of European NbS

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1. Introduction

This report presents a comprehensive literature review on the valuation of biodiversity and nature-based solutions (NbS) in Europe. The review is confined to studies conducted within Europe for several compelling reasons. Firstly, the development of European Union (EU) policies, particularly the EU taxonomy for sustainable investments, has spurred a growing interest in investing and evaluating NbS within the region. This policy framework aims to guide sustainable investment decisions, making Europe a case study for understanding the valuation of NbS.

Secondly, our focus on Europe allows us to examine a setting where institutions are robust and markets are well-functioning. This context ensures that evaluations of NbS primarily address non-market goods and services, which are often overlooked in traditional market-based assessments. By concentrating on non-market valuations, we can gain insights into the broader ecological and societal benefits provided by NbS, which are crucial for policy-making and sustainable development.

The primary objective of our literature review is to provide a comprehensive overview of the methodologies employed in valuing NbS, as well as the types of environments and specific NbS that have been investigated. We aim to identify the strengths and limitations of various valuation approaches and to highlight key findings and trends in the existing body of academic work. Our review focuses exclusively on published academic studies to ensure the credibility and rigor of the information presented.

2. Search criteria and information

The literature search employed a variety of public databases, including EVRI and ENVALUE, as well as Google Scholar, Scopus, and cross-references from primary articles. Our inclusion criteria encompassed all types of English-language primary published studies that focus on the valuation of NbS and biodiversity by European citizens. The keywords used in the search were: “value” OR “valuation” OR “economic value” OR “economic benefit*” OR “willingness to pay” OR “WTP” OR “preference” OR “stated preference” OR “contingent valuation” OR “dichotomous choice” OR “choice experiment” OR “stated choice” OR “travel cost” OR “hedonic pricing” OR “market price” AND “biodiversity”.

From the resulting list of studies, we specifically identified those conducted in Europe, with a particular emphasis on geographically specific NbS. This approach allowed us to focus on the unique environmental and socio-economic contexts within Europe, ensuring that our review is relevant to the region's specific needs and challenges. The information extracted from the papers included various details such as the type of land and ecosystem services provided, the valuation methods used, and the types of respondents involved. Specifically, the type of land refers to different environments such as urban areas, rural landscapes, forests, wetlands, and coastal regions. Ecosystem services encompass a wide range of benefits provided by these environments, including provisioning services (e.g., food and water supply), regulating services (e.g., climate regulation and

flood control), cultural services (e.g., recreational and aesthetic value), and supporting services (e.g., nutrient cycling and soil formation).

The valuation methods used in the papers are diverse and aim to quantify the economic value of these ecosystem services. For instance, the travel cost method (which is one of the revealed preference methods), estimates the value of recreational sites by examining the expenses incurred by visitors traveling to these locations. Stated preferences methods, such as contingent valuation and choice experiments, involve surveys where respondents express their willingness to pay for specific environmental benefits or changes. These methods help in understanding the total value of ecosystem services from the perspective of different stakeholders and allow for capturing both use-, option-, and non-use values of these services.

3. Results

In Table 1, we report all the papers that were included in the final literature review. In total, there are 42 papers. Stakeholders include users of ecosystem services—for example, park visitors or farmers who depend on soil fertility—as well as citizens who gain indirect use-values from these services or gain non-use values. In our analysis we distinguish between respondents who actively engage with and gain from a particular natural environment, labelled Citizens (local) in Table 1, and those who do not interact with that specific area but still derive benefits at a broader scale; the latter group is captured through a nationally representative sample and labelled Citizens (national) in Table 2.

Table 1. List of studies from 19 European countries

Reference	Country	Method	Type of environment	Type of ESS	Target population	Type of NbS
Chae et al. (2012)	U.K.	TCM	Marine	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Alessandro et al. (2022)	Italy	TCM	Forest	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Latinopoulos et al. (2016)	Greece	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage
Getzner et al. (2016)	Croatia	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Juutinen et al. (2011)	Finland	CE	Forest	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Czajkowski et al. (2009)	Poland	CE	Forest	Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect
Black et al. (2010)	U.K.	CVM	Grassland	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage, protect
Boeri et al. (2020)	U.K.	CE	Coast	Biodiversity, Recreation, Cultural	Citizens (national)	Restore
Crespo-Cebada et al. (2020)	Spain	CE	Forest, River	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage, restore
Ratzke (2023)	Germany	HPM	Urban	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage, protect
Getzner & Švajda (2015)	Slovakia	CVM	Forest	Recreation	Visitor	Manage
Jobstvogt (2014)	Scotland	CE	Marine	Provisioning, Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect
Tonin (2019)	Italy	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore

Tonin (2017)	Italy	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore
Rousseau & Fuertes (2020)	Netherlands	CE, TCM	Rivers & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Getzner (2017)	Poland	CVM	Forest	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Grazhdani (2024)	Albania, Greece, Macedonia	CVM, TCM	Rives & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Tonin (2018)	Italy	CVM	Marine	Biodiversity, Recreation	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect, restore
Tyrväinen, L. (2001)	Finland	CVM	Urban	Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Grilli et al. (2018)	Ireland, U.K.	TCM	Rivers & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Simões (2013)	Portugal	CE, TCM	Forest	Recreation	Visitors	Manage, protect
Collins (2017)	U.K.	CE	Urban	Biodiversity	Visitors	Manage
Brandolini (2006)	Italy	CVM	Rivers & lakes	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Riepe et al. (2019)	Germany, France, Norway, Sweden	CE	Rivers & lakes	Biodiversity, Provisioning, Recreation	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore
Meyerhoff (2019)	Germany	CE	Rivers & lakes	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Meyerhoff (2009)	Germany	CE	Forest	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage
Varela (2017)	Belgium, Germany	CE	Crop, Forest, Grassland	Biodiversity	Citizens (local)	Manage, restore
Horne (2005)	Finland	CE	Forest	Biodiversity, Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Tyrväinen & Miettinen (2000)	Finland	HPM	Urban	Biodiversity, Recreation, Noise reduction, Air quality, Aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Manage
Willis & Benson (1988)	U.K.	TCM	Forest, Grassland	Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Christie & Rayment (2012)	U.K.	CE	Grassland, Inland wetland, Coastal	Provisioning, supporting, climate regulation, flood regulation, recreation, biodiversity, cultural	Citizens (national)	Manage, protect
Chen et al. (2014b)	Belgium	CVM	Grassland	Regulating, supporting, flood regulation, recreation	Citizens (national)	Restore
Mell et al. (2013)	U.K.	CVM	Urban	Aesthetics, air quality	Citizens (local)	Manage

Birol et al. (2009)	Poland	CE	Wetland	Flood regulation, biodiversity, recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Bishop (1992)	U.K.	CVM	Urban	Recreation	Visitors	Manage
Hanley & Knight (1992)	U.K.	CVM	Urban	Biodiversity, Recreation, Aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Protect
Bertram et al. (2017)	Germany	CE	Urban	Biodiversity, Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage
Giergiczny & Kronenberg (2014)	Poland	CE	Urban	Local climate regulation, aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Manage, restore
Hampson et al. (2017)	U.K.	CE	Rivers & lakes	Biodiversity, Recreation	Citizens (local)	Manage, restore
Tu et al. (2016)	France	CE	Urban	Recreation, Aesthetics	Citizens (local)	Manage
Masiero et al. (2022)	Italy	PFM	Forest	Provisioning, supporting, biodiversity, recreation, aesthetics	Citizens (national)	Manage, restore
Faure et al. (2024)	France	PFM	Crop	Provisioning, supporting	Citizens (local)	Restore

Table 2. Main characteristics of valuation studies on biodiversity and NbS in Europe

Method	Environment		Population		ESS		
CVM	36%	Marine	17%	Citizens (local)	36%	Recreation	71%
CE	45%	Cropland	5%	Citizens (national)	24%	Biodiversity	57%
TCM	17%	Forest	29%	Visitors	40%	Provisioning	12%
HPM	5%	Grassland	12%			Noise reduc.	2%
PFM	5%	Urban	24%	Type		Air quality	5%
				Manage	90%	Aesthetics	12%
		Rivers & lakes	14%	Protect	19%	Climate reg.	5%
				Restore	29%	Supporting	10%

Table 2 shows that the most common study environments have been forest and urban areas, followed by marine areas. A large majority of the studies utilize stated preference methods, with more than 80% of the studies employing either the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) or Choice Experiments (CE). These methods are particularly favored because they allow researchers to directly elicit individuals' valuations of non-market goods, such as environmental benefits, by presenting hypothetical scenarios and asking respondents to state their willingness to pay for specific outcomes. These methods do not rely on existing data to elicit environmental benefits; instead, individuals' preferences are elicited by using surveys or interviews. The

widespread use of CVM and CE underscores their importance and reliability in capturing all aspects of the economic value of ecosystem services and natural resources. In contrast, only a small fraction of the studies, about 5%, have employed the Hedonic Pricing Method (HPM). HPM is typically used to estimate economic values for ecosystems or environmental services that directly affect market prices, such as property values. The limited use of HPM may be attributed to the complexity of isolating environmental attributes from other factors influencing market prices, making it less prevalent in the literature.

Similarly, another 5% of the studies have utilized the Production Function Method (PFM). PFM is used to assess the contribution of natural resources to the production of goods and services, often in agricultural or industrial contexts. The relatively low adoption of PFM could be due to the specific data requirements and the need for detailed knowledge of the production processes involved, which may not be readily available for all study areas.

Since many studies focus on recreational values, the Travel Cost Method (TCM) has been used in 17% of the studies. TCM estimates the economic value of recreational sites by analyzing the travel expenses incurred by visitors. This method is particularly useful for valuing recreational sites such as parks, rivers, and forests, where visitors' travel and time costs can serve as a proxy for their willingness to pay for access to these natural benefits.

Moreover, 40% of the studies concentrate on visitors to Nature-based Solutions (NbS). These visitors could include individuals frequenting urban parks, anglers fishing in rivers, or bird watchers exploring forests. The focus on visitors highlights the importance of direct use values associated with NbS, as these natural areas provide significant recreational and aesthetic benefits to the public.

Even many of the stated preference surveys primarily target the direct use values of NbS. These surveys often involve respondents who directly interact with and benefit from the natural environment, such as residents or frequent visitors. Naturally, many stated preference studies focus on citizens living near the NbS, as these individuals are more likely to experience and appreciate the benefits provided by these natural areas.

However, there is a minority of studies that include a nationwide sample of citizens. These studies aim to capture a broader perspective on the value of NbS, considering the views and preferences of individuals who may not directly interact with the specific natural areas but still recognize their importance for overall environmental health, societal well-being, or who just value the pure existence of the natural area.

4. Conducting discussion

This report has provided a comprehensive analysis of data extracted from the reviewed papers, focusing on the type of land and ecosystem services provided, the valuation methods used, and the types of respondents involved. The reviewed papers covered a diverse range of environments, including urban areas, rural landscapes, forests, wetlands, and coastal regions. These environments provide a wide array of ecosystem services, such as provisioning services (e.g., food and water supply), regulating services (e.g., climate regulation and flood control), cultural services (e.g., recreational and aesthetic value), and supporting services (e.g., nutrient cycling and soil formation). The valuation methods employed in these studies were varied, with

stated preference methods being the most used. In conclusion, the reviewed papers offer valuable insights into the economic value of ecosystem services and the benefits they provide to society. The literature review revealed gaps in data, particularly in certain environments and services. Some ecosystem services, such as supporting services, are less frequently studied, leading to an incomplete understanding of their value. Additionally, certain regions and types of land may be underrepresented in the existing research. While the use of varied valuation methods is a strength, it also presents challenges. Each method has its own set of strengths and limitations, which can affect the accuracy and reliability of the results. For instance, the travel cost method may not fully capture the non-market values of ecosystem services, while stated preferences methods can be influenced by hypothetical bias.

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